
D3.1

RAPP-JR guidelines and context

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CoARA Boost CF1

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation program under Grant Agreement No. 101131826

Vienna, November 2025

1 Sum-up RAPP-JR

This deliverable is the main outcome of the project RAPP-JR and includes the guidelines and recommendations as well as the underlying empirical work for these guidelines.

Main achievements and most important outcomes of RAPP-JR:

Part A summarizes the concrete guidelines and recommendations preparing a CoARA action plan on 3 topics:

- Excellence in non-academic applied research
- Inclusive Careers
- Open Science

Part B contains the baseline work for developing these guidelines:

- The policy analysis of European as well as JR-internal documents
- A discussion of digital notebooks as instrument to raise awareness on individual practices relevant in the context of CoARA

PART A Guidelines

- 1 Guideline 1: Excellence in non-academic applied research
- 2 Guideline 2: Inclusive Careers
- 3 Guideline 3: Open Science

Methodology

In course of the RAPP-JR project three Guidelines have been developed, which contain concrete recommendations for actions for a CoARA action plan at Joanneum Reserearch.

These guidelines were developed as collective process, co-created by the RAPP taskforce (JR management), JR employees and RAPP-JR project team

RAPP-JR

Reforming Assessment Policies and Practices in Joanneum Research (JR)

Guideline 1: Excellence in non-academic applied research

Helene Schiffbänker, Gerit Anders
Florian Holzinger

Excellence in

Applied Non-University Research (1)

WHY?

- Excellence is core when it comes to the assessment of research, researchers and research performing organisations (RPO)
- JR as applied non-university research RO conducts research strongly in collaboration with stakeholders from industry and society
- How can excellence in a RO which is part of the business enterprise sector (BES) be best measured?

Excellence in Applied Non-University Research (2)

WHAT?

- To make JR employees aware of this topic, they were invited to reflect on their thoughts and experiences on excellence for about 4 weeks in notebooks and then reflect on their experiences collectively.
- JR management was invited to reflect on the topic in interviews
- RAPP-JR reached out to other applied non-university RO to initiate a discourse on this (ISTA, AIT, Forschung Austria)
- Overall aim: develop a sectoral perspective (BES) on excellence

Excellence in Applied Non-University Research (3)

NUTSHELL / CONCLUSIONS:

- Across JR institutes, relevance of h-index etc. varies
- Excellence indicators: are crucial JR-internally to provide clarity on what counts as excellence (career prospects)
 - What (career step) can I achieve?
 - What (excellence) is needed to achieve this?
 - What do I get when I have achieved this?
- JR excellence criteria should be broadened to reflect applied research realities = expand the academic notion of excellence
- Excellence in applied research is closely linked to innovation. Innovation requires experimental spirit and learning culture to critically reflecting on challenges and to learn from mistakes

Overview Guideline 1

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Guideline1	Recommendations for action	
<p>Excellence in non-academic and applied sciences at JR</p> <p><i>How can excellent performance be best reflected at JR?</i></p>	<p>1: Revise excellence criteria</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Applied research-specific criteria: duration of stakeholder cooperation, project benefits, interdisciplinary/economically successful projects • Relativise H-index
	<p>2: Formally establish inclusive excellence criteria</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Operationalise criteria, including indicators • Anchor them in strategic documents: Internal excellence report etc. • Establish control mechanisms and responsibility
	<p>3: Disseminating inclusive excellence assessment</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communicate internally: Let employees know when their performance is excellent and subsequently offer career prospects
	<p>4: Apply inclusive excellence assessment</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Standardise in recruitment and development interivews
	<p>5: Promoting a culture of learning</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide structures for learning from mistakes • Establish mentoring and buddy systems

Recommendation 1:
***Revise and expand excellence
criteria (1)***

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The number of publications and the quality of the journals are relevant success criteria at JR.

These should and can be expanded to include the following criteria, which were identified by RAPP-JR as relevant for excellence in the applied research:

- Projects range from research ideas to market readiness
- Cooperation with stakeholders during and after the research process
- Benefits achieved from research results
- Economic success of projects
- Interdisciplinary teams combine different skills

Recommendation 1:
***Revise and expand excellence
criteria (2)***

**Concrete suggestion for expanded criteria in the JR
excellence report:**

- **Duration** of cooperations with stakeholders from industry and society
- Self-assessment of the (societal) impact of research projects
 - Assessment matrix and/or open question
- Proportion of interdisciplinary projects
- Proportion of projects with economic success
- Relativise quantitative evaluation criteria (e.g. H-index)

Recommendation 2: Formally establish inclusive excellence criteria

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- Define an expanded understanding of excellence: criteria, indicators, etc.
- Anchor or operationalise in strategic documents
 - Excellence report
 - Annual research plan
- Define control and responsibility

Recommendation 3:

Disseminate inclusive excellence assessment

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- Communicate and discuss expanded understanding of excellence within JR
- To give employees the feeling that their performance is excellent and is viewed as such = provide security/**convey prospects**

Recommendation 4:

Apply inclusive excellence assessment

- Adjust assessment system for annual performance evaluation of employees based on the new performance indicators
- Apply excellence criteria in a standardised manner in selection/promotion interviews
 - e.g. “How have you taken social benefits into account in your research to date?” (ISTA)

Recommendation 5:

Promote a culture of learning

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- Create space and structures for the generation of new ideas and innovations
 - Links to existing formats and experiences
 - Business areas
 - Internal workshops like Technologie@JR
- Foster and establish mentoring and buddy-systems to support learning (culture)
- Add indicators to monitor

Suggestion for assessment indicators:

- Number of new topics addressed and their implementation
- „Innovation-meetings“
- Documented learning processes and „learning projects“
 - Qualitative description of non-achievements of objections
 - Mistakes as positive learning experiences
- Use of mentoring and buddy systems

RAPP-JR

Reforming Assessment Policies and Practices in Joanneum Research (JR)

Guideline 2: Inclusive Careers

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Florian Holzinger

Inclusive Careers at JR

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- Careers and excellence are interconnected in 2 ways:

Definition of excellence:
Excellence criteria define what is needed to make an excellent career

Expectations on excellent researchers:
Recruiting / promotion decisions build on how excellence criteria are met

- JR career performance assessment: conducted annually by supervisor in development meeting (*Entwicklungsgespräch*).
- How can excellence be assessed in different disciplines and fields of work (research, technical support, administration)?
- Which activities contribute to excellent research, how are they reflected in different career tracks (research management)?
- How can recruitment processes be best formalized?

Inclusive careers at JR

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- At JR, few women are in (scientific) leadership positions
 - project management
 - research group management
 - institute management
- Project management was identified as important step for leadership role
 - re-evaluate position of project management in career tracks
 - get more people in project management positions (focus on women!)
 - provide support for researchers starting project management

Overview Guideline 2

Guideline 2	Recommendations for action	
<p>Inclusive careers</p> <p><i>How can more inclusive (non-linear) careers in non-university research institutions be fostered?</i></p>	<p>6: Make management positions more attractive</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PR campaign: Portraying leaders in all their diversity • Expand narrative assessment elements • Enable professional mobility within JR • Enabling shared leadership (see gender equality plan of JR)
	<p>7: Make project management positions more attractive</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communicate project management as step towards leadership roles • PR campaign: „Project management is cool (working title)!“ • Establish broader career tracks (research management)
	<p>8: Formally establish a more inclusive understanding of project management</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assess and communicate project management positions in a new way in the competence development concept • Make management accountable for achieving a more diversity (by gender, age, etc) in project management
	<p>9: Support for project managers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Guideline for project management (part of JR QM system) • Targeted training • Low-threshold entry (small or JR-internal project, co-lead) • Constant support (buddy for on-the-job training)
	<p>10: Optimise recruitment processes</p>	<p>Transparent selection processes (criteria, decision-makers, male-female ration on long-list, short-list, etc) in recruitment and promotion</p>

Recommendation 6:

Make management positions more attractive

- PR campaign: Portray leaders in all their diversity (by age, internal/external career, cultural background, etc.)
- Expand narrative assessment elements: raise awareness for their benefits
- Enable professional mobility within JR: e.g. from institutes to head quarter
- Enabling shared leadership (JR gender equality plan)

Recommendation 7: Make project management positions more attractive

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- Communicate project management as a step towards leadership roles
- Launch PR campaign: “*Project management is cool!*“ (working title)
- Establish career paths beyond research: present career opportunities like research management

“Creating Framework Conditions for Research Management to Strengthen the European Research Area”

Source: EC(2025) „The European Competence Framework for research managers“

Recommendation 8: Establish inclusive understanding of project management

- Anchor project management (PM) as career step in JR competence development concept, raise awareness for it
- Integrate PM in HR tools: e.g. development talk guideline
- Make research group leaders / directors accountable for achieving more diversity (by gender) for project managers
 - Define possible indicators for monitoring success, e.g. proportion of new project leaders per year, concentration of project management positions

Recommendation 9: Provide support for project managers

- Guideline for project management: linked to JR quality management
- Targeted trainings
- Constant support in training on-the-job: establish buddy system for (new) project managers
- Low-threshold entry for new project managers
 - continuous involvement in acquisition of projects
 - start with leading small or JR-internal project, co-lead projects

Recommendation 10: Formalize selection processes

High-quality selection processes in recruitment and promotion are characterised by transparency and inclusion.

- Establish selection criteria and make them equally accessible to applicants and evaluators
- Apply criteria systematically: evaluate all applicants using the **same criteria** and **apply all criteria equally to all applicants**
- Make number and male-female ratio of applicants transparent: all applicants, long list, short list, interviewees etc
- Formalise selection process:
 - Define **who** (which function) exactly is involved **in which step** of the selection processes for various positions (recruiting employee, research group leader, directors, lead of administrative units)
 - Define who is responsible for **final decision**
 - Set a **time frame** for the process: how long will different steps take

RAPP-JR

Reforming Assessment Policies and Practices in Joanneum Research (JR)

Guideline 3: Open Science

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Open Science (OS) at JR

- Increasing relevance of OS due to funding requirements
- No uniform standards regarding OS, different conditions at different JR institutes
- Industrial collaborations: limitations for data disclosure

How can open science be implemented and practiced in a non-university research environment?

- Disclosure of research material (maintenance of software and data) means additional work: who pays?
- Open Access and science communication are seen as positive opportunity
- Scientists need support and guidance regarding OS

Overview Guideline 3

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Guideline	Recommendations for action	
<p>Open Science (OS)</p> <p><i>How can JR best implement Open Science?</i></p>	<p>11: OS knowledge hub</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Good practices and contact persons by topic (ethics, data management, AI, contracts for Intellectual Property Rights (IPR), etc.) • OS tools and services • Data management plans
	<p>12: OS Guideline</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Summary of everything one needs to know including links to knowledge hub
	<p>13: OS implementation</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Set strategic direction (especially with regard to industrial partners) as basis for specific regulations • Accountability of project managers for OS in each project • PR campaign for awareness raising on OS • OS trainings

Recommendation 11: Open Science knowledge hub

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- Relevant topics
 - Ethics
 - AI
 - Data management plans and precessing
 - Information on open access journals freely available for researchers
 - Most relevant publications on OS (policies, papers)
- Good practices
 - Reference projects on data management plans, IPR contracts etc
 - Overview of tools and services
- Information about contact persons in context of OS: competencies, responsibilities, e.g. IPR agreements
- Internal trainings on OS
- OS Knowledge Hub: should be accessable via intranet

Recommendation 12: Open Science guideline

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- Summary of everything researchers need to know about OS
- Including links to information in OS knowledge hub

Recommendation 13: Open Science implementation

- Set strategic direction for OS in JR (especially with regard to industrial partners) as a basis for specific regulations in institutes: e.g. what can be disclosed
- OS responsibility of project leaders
 - Decisions have to be made for each project
- PR campaign
 - for awareness raising on OS
 - for disseminating information about support formats
- OS trainings

PART B Methodology

1 Policy Analysis

1.1 APPROACH

The objective of the document analysis was first to capture the ongoing discourse about the three topics (excellence, inclusive careers and open science) through analysing relevant national and EU framework documents. A second objective was to conceive the current status quo within JR regarding the three topics by analysing JR-internal policy documents.

The findings informed and guided the development of further data collection instruments in WP2, as the digital notebooks for employees and the guideline for the qualitative interviews with the management.

1.2 DATA

In course of the document analysis, 37 documents have been analysed. While five documents were internal policy documents from Joanneum Research, the rest were recommendations and guidelines for the reformation of research assessment from the EU, the European Council, CoARA and documents on national level and international publications.

When analysing this data, the following observations were relevant: The way scientific excellence and researchers are assessed shapes research practices. In a critical perspective, scholars showed how the existing measures for excellent research led to a reproduction of inequalities in the research ecosystem and therefore see a necessity to reform the measurements and extend the concept of excellence (see Jong et.al. 2021).

In this study, the focus lies in on the three areas excellence, inclusive careers and open science. However, in course of the document analysis it became clear that these areas are related and approaching these areas separately would be unrewarding.

- On the one hand, measures for recruitment are strongly connected to measures for excellence. Therefore, a more promising differentiation would be assessment criteria for research units, for single researchers and for single contributions (see European Commission 2021).
- On the other hand, open science is considered as a desirable indicator for excellent research, because the character of open science is associated with establishing robust quality control processes (see European Commission 2024).

Therefore, the results of the document analysis are not presented separated, but in an overlapping manner. Therefore, firstly the discussion about the reflection of well-established indicators for excellence are summarised and secondly identified additional inclusive criteria, which are recommended in the literature, are presented. Additional to the findings, the state of the art for every aspect at Joanneum Research is presented, based on the analysis of the internal policy documents.

1.3 MAIN FINDINGS

A challenge with established quantitative excellence indicators is that they produce an exclusive ecosystem. Assessing researchers and research units by quantitative indicators like university rankings, number of publications and citations causes the so-called Mathew effect. It describes that those researchers or research units that are rated higher, get more attention and therefore have a greater impact. This system favours those who are already well established, e.g. articles from researchers with a high publication rate are more likely to be published and cited more often than an article from a researcher with a lower publication rate and leave little possibility for newcomers to make an impact (see Jong et.al. 2021).

Another problem described in the literature is that research practices mean a variety of activities, which are not covered by established indicators, like **publications** or **acquired funding**. Activities that are often shielded are **teaching** and **supervision of students, mentoring, successful project management** or **dissemination of research outputs**. So, by assessing researchers only by one field, researchers are forced to concentrate on that and need to neglect the other fields (see Jong et.al. 2021).

It was shown already many times that especially **women are excluded** by the assessment by traditional indicators, because they are rather active in fields which are not covered by the indicators like multidisciplinary research, research papers that addresses SDGs or are policy relevant (see Bayazit 2024).

Furthermore, aiming for one common understanding of excellence and indicators which make all contributions comparable is problematic as well, because in **different contexts, disciplines and regions** different circumstances and expectations are found (see Jong et.al. 2021). The challenge in forming indicators is to strike a balance between achieving comparability and considering contextual differences.

1.3.1 Funding

The acquired funds are considered as an important indicator for excellent research. Therefore, it is even more important that funding is distributed in a fair and inclusive way. Research Funding Organisations play a crucial role here. It could be shown that excellence-based funding schemes, where scientific performance is mostly measured by **quantitative indicators**, widely **neglect social relevance, transdisciplinary research** and **high-risk research**. Due to that, a discourse emerged about alternative funding schemes, supporting especially these aspects. One promising approach are performance-based funding schemes tied with national evaluation processes. Performance-based funding schemes rely primarily on peer review processes, but also on bibliometric analysis of outputs (see Jong et.al. 2021, p.14). Another alternative approach considered in Germany is funds for persons instead of funds for projects. However, experiences with such funding schemes are rare and therefore it is not clear whether they reduce or reproduce inequalities in the research ecosystem (see Ploder et.al. 2023).

1.3.1.1 State of the Art at JR

The acquisition of funding is crucial at JR since all research units rely mainly on external funding. However, it is not implemented as quantitative assessment criterion for excellence. Yet particularly outstanding achievements in the acquisition of funding for research units are positively emphasised in the internal documents (see Joanneum Research “Entwicklungsplan” 2023-2027, p. 35, 52, 54 and Joanneum Research “Wissenschaftliche Exzellenzkriterien”, p. 35).

1.3.2 Publications

The number of publications is another well-established indicator for excellent research. It is criticised for a few reasons:

- the focus on publications leads to the negligence of other aspects of excellence, which are tried to be included through additional excellent indicators. When it comes to publications, the Mathew effect emerges.
- It has been shown that female researchers have a lower publishing and citation rate. They are more often listed as co-authors than their male counterpart, as female researchers are more active in other areas like teaching activities, administrative work or dissemination of research results (see Bayazit 2024). In order to make the publication process more inclusive, it is necessary to find a way how these other aspects get more attention.

The original idea behind publications is to distribute and communicate research results to the scientific community, so further scientific work is able to benefit from it. By supporting open science, this aim can be achieved while other aspects of research get more attention at the same time. By making publications freely available, not only the whole research community benefits from it, but also the research process becomes more transparent. The idea of **open science** goes further than only publicly available publications. In this context it is recommended to **make the whole research process more transparent**, being transparent with methodology and data and **communicate the results** not only with the scientific community, but also with **society and politics**. By doing so, other aspects of research practices should get more attention (see German Science and Humanities Council 2022).

The publication process strongly depends on the Peer Review process, however, this process is also strongly criticised. Rise et.al. (2025) argue that the Peer Review process reproduce asymmetric power relations within research community. Jong et.al. (2021) also argue that the publishing process connected with the peer review process is keen to undervalue high-risk research and transdisciplinary research. The reason why especially transdisciplinary research tendentially gets more negative feedback in the peer review process is that very often the peer group does not offer experts in this field. This applies especially in a language group, in a limited group of peers, it's very often not possible to find a suitable peer for high-risky, complex or transdisciplinary research (see Ploder et.al. 2023).

A last idea how the publishing process could become more inclusive that could have been identified in the literature is to **broaden the definition of publications by grey literature** such as policy papers (see Jong et.al. 2021).

1.3.2.1 State of the Art at JR

At JR the number of publications is one quantitative indicator for scientific excellence among others and functions to assess the research units. The amount of open access publications is not considered, but other aspects of scientific communication of outputs, like public appearances or presentations are considered by the assessment criteria. The state of the art of other more inclusive criteria is described below in the respective chapters.

1.3.2.2 Additional inclusive Indicators

Because of the exclusive character of quantitative assessment criteria, efforts have been made among others by the European Commission to foster a more intense use of qualitative criteria in research assessment. In the following chapter, some of potential alternative additional indicators are

described. These criteria are applicable in assessment of single contributions, researchers and research units and should be considered on all these levels, in recruitment processes as well as in grant allocation (see European Commission 2021).

1.3.3 Teaching activities

Teaching activities are considered as a crucial part of research practice and scientific excellence, because the new generation of researchers depend on the knowledge that is imparted through teaching activities. However, often researchers do not have enough resources to focus or specialise on teaching. This plays a role especially in the discourse about scientific career paths. The study about scientific cultures in Germany suggests as a solution to **foster heterogeneous career paths**. The authors argue that not every aspect of excellence can be expected from every researcher, therefore it would be promising for researchers to focus or specialise on one aspect, like teaching for example (see Ploder et.al. 2023).

1.3.3.1 State of the Art at JR

Teaching activities are considered in the assessment indicators for scientific excellence at JR. It is measured by the semester periods per week held for each research unit. Not only lectures are considered, but also supervision of students on Bachelor-, Master- or PhD-Level.

1.3.4 Societal impact

Including the societal impact of outcomes in research assessment processes is promoted intensively by the European Union. Jong et.al. (2021) mention in this context **mission oriented funding programmes**. The authors mention one quantification of the societal and political impact of research, the Research Excellence **Framework** (REF) impact “is defined as an effect on, change or benefit to the economy, society, culture, public policy or services, health, the environment or quality of life, beyond academia (Jong et.al. 2021, p. 29).

The fact that science must make a contribution to society and good coexistence is also included as an important point in the Austrian Action Plan for the European Research Area (see Bundesministerium 2022).

Scientific contributions from female researchers have rather social and political relevance, are cited more often in policy documents. Therefore, Bayazat (2024) recommends to apply a broad range of indicators to measure the quality of research and these should include societal and policy impact.

1.3.4.1 State of the Art at JR

Due to the application-orientated character of the research at JR, it is fundamentally designed to create added value for society, politics and the environment. This aspect is part of the general mission of the company. However, the **societal or environmental impact is not considered in the excellence criteria**. It is rather assumed that socially relevant research is supported by the structure and mission of the company and the application-oriented character.

1.3.5 Science Communication

Science communication and public engagement are considered as crucial part of scientific work. Research activities should be communicated and disseminated not only among the scientific community, but also publicly in a way non-specialist and not trained people are able to understand. This public engagement is beneficial for both sides. On the one hand, it improves the public understanding of science and the acceptance for it. On the other hand, it helps researchers to better understand public

interests. Therefore, scientific communication is strongly linked to fostering socially relevant research (see European Commission 2005).

1.3.5.1 State of the Art at JR

Science communication with the research community and the public is covered by different indicators for excellence. These indicators are

- events or presentations at companies,
- public events and appearances or
- presentations within the scientific community, for example on conferences.

1.3.6 Open Science

By fostering Open Science and open access publications, scientific communication and public engagement should also be supported (see German Science and Humanities Council 2022). The knowledge exchange and cooperation between the scientific community, the public and policymakers are crucial for progress within society: this should be achieved by supporting open access research.

A transformation of the research system to open science is complex. All relevant stakeholders, researchers but also RFOs, policymakers, all kind of research-support staff and the public need to work together (see Baraas et.al. 2020). In this context, language issues are discussed intensively. On the one hand, **research that concern locally relevant issues** should be available in the local language. On the other hand as many research outputs should be translated from the local language into English, so that a broad community is able to access and read it. When it comes to OS, besides regional differences and circumstances, **discipline-related differences** should be considered (see Rochambeau 2024).

Open Science does not only mean open access research, but includes different aspects. The main idea regarding OS is to make the entire research progress and all its aspects more transparent (see German Science and Humanities Council 2022). One aspect of it, public engagement, is already explained separately in the previous chapter. Here are some additional important aspects of it.

1.3.6.1 Open Data

One of the most important aspects of OS is the openness of research data, which is recommended to be made available according to the FAIR principles (see Baraas et.al. 2020). Challenges in this regard are

- (a) the convenient infrastructures: here RPOs are responsible to provide a useful framework for data management, sustainable infrastructure for data and metadata storage.
- (b) data protection securities, especially in the area of personal data, which can only be published if it is completely anonymised (see Rochambeau 2024).
- (c) As already mentioned before, the transformation to an Open Science ecosystem is only possible by involving all relevant stakeholders. RFOs must provide a framework for supporting Open Science and assuring its quality. In order to do so, the European Commission (2024) implemented the **EOSC initiative**.

1.3.6.2 Open Methodology

Besides the openness of the results and used or generated data, the methodology should also be made available and transparent, so other researchers can reproduce or validate research processes (see Baraas et.al. 2020).

1.3.6.3 Open Source Software

It is recommended that researchers should - whenever possible - make use of open-source software, because it contributes to making the research process more transparent. On the other side, whenever researchers develop software, it is recommended to make it publicly available (see Baraas et.al. 2020).

1.3.6.4 Open Educational Resources

The idea of OS also influenced the principles of teaching. Researchers and all other types of stakeholders are encouraged to produce and promote open educational resources, so students can profit from the existing material (see Rochambeau 2024).

1.3.6.5 Citizen Science

Citizen Science is a specific way of involving the public in a research process, where citizens take an active role and are involved intentionally. Citizen Science has the potential to support scientific communication, public engagement, OS generally and socially relevant research at the same time and is therefore considered as very promising (see Baraas et.al. 2020).

1.3.6.6 Open Peer Review

There have been some problems identified with the established peer review process. Approaches to make the peer review process more transparent are trying to solve these problems (see Baraas et.al. 2020).

1.3.6.6.1 State of the Art at JR

While aspects of scientific communication are considered by the assessment criteria, aspects of open science are not included. However, in strategic documents fostering open access research and the use of open source software are mentioned.

1.3.7 Multidisciplinary

Multi-, inter- or transdisciplinary research is recommended to be included as an excellence criteria, since it has been proven that this kind of research has been neglected by existing structures. Although, multidisciplinary research has a great potential to address current challenges for society, this kind of research has been rather unsuccessful by excellence-based funding programmes.

Problems with multidisciplinary research are the communication between disciplines and the peer review process (see Jong et.al. 2021). The assessment of multidisciplinary research is more complex than single discipline research, and it is more complicated to select appropriate peers for the review process. The reason why multidisciplinary research as well as risky research approaches have been underestimated often in the peer review process is that the peers involved are not able to assess the approaches accordingly (see Ploder et.al. 2023). Composing panels differently would be an approach here (Rice et.al 2025).

1.3.7.1 State of the Art at JR

At JR multidisciplinary research plays a crucial role, since the core business is applied research and this often requires multidisciplinary approaches. Therefore, at JR cooperation and joint research activities within JR or with external research units and industry are fostered intensively. Already, as the internal strategic documents prove, fruitful cooperation and collaborations between different units within JR and externally are established and will be further consolidated. However, **multidisciplinary so far research is not considered by the quantitative assessment criteria.**

1.3.8 Mobility

The geographical, disciplinary and sectoral mobility of researchers is recommended to be considered positively for excellence, as well as in the understanding of career development and recruitment. However, it is recommended to not use it as a knock-out criteria. Geographical mobility is tied to internationalisation and career progress, but researchers with a local focus and priorities should not be disadvantaged by fostering that (see Jong et.al. 2021). The challenge here is to implement a positive connotation of mobility in grant allocation and recruitment of researchers, but at the same time not overestimate it (see European Commission 2020).

What is requested is an assessment of research careers that acknowledges the variety of research careers and its benefits and at the same time avoid any type of discrimination.

1.3.8.1 State of the Art at JR

In the strategy of JR, a development towards a positive connotation of all forms of mobility is presented as supportable and it is also considered by the assessment criteria, the indicator is Stays abroad for further education, scientific co-operation. However, it is not implemented in the formal guidelines for recruitment explicitly.

1.3.9 Focus on Research Process

Some approaches recommend paying more attention to aspects of the research process itself in the assessment, so here the most important aspects are explained.

- What is considered most relevant is the ability to **work together** in a research team and the **motivation of a single researcher** (see Jong.et.al).
- When it comes to leading positions, the ability to successfully **lead a research** or project team becomes important. The CoARA working group “Reforming Academic Career Assessment” argues that **management skills** - similar to teaching skills – are not covered by the established assessment criteria.
- Another aspect is **cooperation** and **networking**. The European Commission aims to provide a framework that favours collaboration between research entities, such as centres of excellence or digital innovation hubs (see European Commission 2020).
- A last aspect is **quality assurance** and the assessment of professional performance. Both aspects are crucial for the reputation of scientific work. The research community is responsible to assure quality of research contributions and researchers. This requires resources and should be considered as a priority. However, researchers often lack of resources to fulfil these responsibilities (see European Commission 2005).

1.3.9.1 State of the Art at JR

The described aspects can be found in the strategic documents of JR in regard to training for employees and mentoring. Further training of employees in their scientific field or management issues has a high priority at JR. JR documents make clear that these aspects are implemented in the company structure and procedures, dedicated financial resources are provided for every company unit, all employees should have the opportunity to receive individualised and high-quality training according to their position and needs. The amount of training days per year per research unit is also one assessment criteria.

Additionally an internal mentoring programme has been implemented at JR some years ago. With a train-the-trainer- approach this aim should be supported even further and assure quality in the training.

1.3.10 Research Careers

One further aspect concerns a more inclusive assessment of research careers. The two main issues here are to recognising and valuing the full range of professional experience, which of course includes avoiding discrimination, but also recognising mobility or career breaks. Further, recognising professionalism at all academic career stages is a major issue. Every career stage has its advantages and its value. Young academics, especially doctoral students and postdocs, should be perceived as professional and competent as senior researchers (see European Commission 2005). Relevant here is the idea of heterogeneous career paths, as already described in the chapter about teaching activities (see Ploder et.al. 2023).

1.3.10.1 State of the Art at JR

The recognition of the full range of professional experience - including forms of mobility and career breaks - are discussed in different contexts in the strategic documents. Especially the interaction and collaboration with economy and industry (**sectoral**) **mobility** is connoted very positively, for example patent registrations or spin-offs. However, geographical mobility is viewed rather critically in the context of JR. In many fields of research, a regional anchoring of scientists is seen as positive.

Furthermore, the company makes an effort to deal with career breaks in the most inclusive way. For example, people who interrupt their career in the company are offered further training and a special onboarding process.

Regarding the recognition of professionalism on all career stages, a level system was implemented for different stages in a scientific career. For each level requirements and objectives are defined regarding training. Especially to support researchers in the PhD stage, a doctoral programme has recently been developed and implemented, which also considers different requirements and needs in the different institutes.

In 2019 a mentoring program has been developed from the diversity department to increase the pool of potential female leaders. It offers the opportunity that managers raise awareness to the promotion of junior staff with focus on female leadership.

1.3.11 Recruiting

Recruitment is closely connected to the topic of research careers. However, it refers not only to the assessment of research careers but rather to the recruitment process itself. According to the literature, the recruitment process should be first tailored to the advertised position, but also be inclusive, efficient and transparent for all concerned parties. In course of the selection process, **people responsible should be suitable**, i.e. should have **a range of knowledge about the field of specialty as well as in diversity and inclusivity**. The selection criteria should be **transparent, accessible for the selection panel in the same way as for the applicant** and take into account the whole range of experience of the candidates, applying quantitative and qualitative criteria. In order to support inclusivity and recognition of career breaks, variations in the chronological order of the CVs should be possible (see European Commission 2005)

1.3.11.1 State of the Art at JR

At JR several efforts are made to make the recruitment process inclusive and avoid discrimination and gender bias. The diversity department has developed a gender-sensitive recruitment guideline, which covers the entire recruitment process:

- The first step is to define the requirements profile for the position to be filled, specify professional and social competences. Therefore, it is emphasized that assessment criteria

and their weighting in the selection process should be defined at the beginning of the process. Further, these criteria should be transparent, measurable and comparable.

- After publishing the employment advertisement, the selection of suitable candidates is the next step. To be inclusive, it is recommended to question whether different target groups and genders are being addressed in the same way at every step and to avoid discrimination.
- While informal recruitment is also possible, i.e. through personal or institutional networks, this process should also be designed to be as inclusive as possible, e.g. female students should be actively approached when recruiting at universities.
- The last step before a decision has to be made is the job interview. The guidelines specify that the interview has to be structured, the assessment criteria have to be transparent, measurable and comparable and the selection panel should be suitable.

In sum, most of the aspect defined by the European Commission for an inclusive recruitment process are considered in the gender sensitive recruitment guideline. However, it is not known to what extent this guideline is applied in practice for the recruitment process.

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2 Notebooks

2.1 METHOD

Digital notebooks are a crucial method in course of the RAPP-JR project. This method is an adaptation of the digital diary study for the given purpose. The digital diary is a qualitative method which collects information remotely instead of collecting data and information actively from participants like in interviews for example. It is often used when behaviour and opinions of costumers, users or other target groups are the epistemological interest. Qualitative interviews or focus group discussions are always situation-based which means the collected data depends on the time and space the method takes place and is only one snapshot. In diary studies, participants self-report their thoughts independently of time, space and the observer, they are only provided with instructions and support. This method is promising when, first time plays a crucial role, second it is favourable that participants are able to choose the moment for reflection by themselves or third there is a risk that the observer would influence the data (see Moran 2018).

2.2 NOTEBOOKS AS INSTRUMENT FOR AWARENESS RAISING

In course of RAPP-JR, the project team aimed to gather information about the personal and independent thoughts from JR researchers about assessment criteria and how they personally aim to be assessed based on their work experience. This process of reflection can make participants think about aspects they would not think about otherwise.

This method is promising because it enables participants to reflect on specific topics and questions independently and over a longer period of time.

The project team decided to call the method 'Notebooks' instead of 'Diary' as it is a simplified form of the diary study method. Also, in the professional context the term "notebook" felt more suitable than "diary". In the literature, an interposed approach to diary studies is recommended, where qualitative interviews are suggested with the study participants before and after the diary-writing phase (see Jarrahi et.al. 2021). This approach has been applied in RAPP in a similar way: group meetings have been conducted before to support the participants how to conduct their tasks. Collective reflections were organised to identify common pattern as well as diverging experiences.

2.3 PARTICIPANTS AND PROCESS

The recruitment of the notebook writers started already at the kick-off event with the scientific staff at JR. The participants of this event (about 20) have been asked actively if they would be interested to become a notebook writer. More efforts have been made through the equal opportunities officers at the institutes to recruit notebook writers.

In the end, 11 researchers representing all departments at JR have been recruited as notebook writers. The notebook-writing phase has been scheduled for April 2025.

Beforehand participants were provided with instructions and guiding questions for the writing process. The guideline has been developed based on the document analysis and along the three topics, whereas notebook writers could choose by themselves if they cover all three topics or less in case those have less relevance.

A Q&A Session with all notebook writers was offered, a summary of the discussed challenges and solutions was shared with all participants. The project team supported the participants also during the writing process. A reflection workshop with all notebook writers had taken place in May.

After the writing phase, the notebooks have been collected, anonymized and analysed by the project team. MAXQDA was used for content analysis. The following chapter sums up the insights gathered through the analysis of the notebooks and this reflection workshop.

2.4 MAIN FINDINGS

The results are presented along the three main topics of the RAPP-JR project, as the notebooks as well as the reflection workshop has been constructed along them.

2.4.1 Scientific excellence

Notebook writers reflected their understanding of scientific excellence as being prestigious and well established in one's scientific field, with that involving different activities. Most of them see international recognition, which manifests itself in invitations to give lectures, invitations for publications, invitation to be a reviewer or a supervisor, as an indication of scientific excellence. It was stated that scientific excellence at JR does not only mean publications, but also acquisition of research funds, dissemination of knowledge and results, teaching and supervising activities. However, these aspects are harder to measure. The writers are aware of the problem with established indicators like number of publications, rankings or impact factors in journals as these indicators can easily be artificially improved; tend to favour already established scientists, institutes or methods.

Applied research is the core business of all institutes at JOANNEUM RESEARCH and this context has different requirements in research assessment than universities. Most scientists at JOANNEUM RESEARCH see a **critical discourse** on excellence as important. Applied research is practically and purposefully oriented and therefore always in line with public interests. In this context, **funding** is the indicator for success rather than publications. In most research projects **publications** are **not even possible** or not desired for different reasons (not considered in the project budget, limitations due to (industry) project partners). Therefore, the number of publications or impact factors are indicators with limited relevance for scientific excellence in that domain. Based on their daily work experiences, an indicator that measures the success rate of funding acquisition or successful delivered contract research projects could rather cover what researchers understand as excellence.

Applied research also goes hand in hand with a different way of working, from which success criteria can also be derived. Work is structured in projects; researchers mostly work in groups and address socially relevant problems often with an interdisciplinary approach. Therefore, measuring the **societal relevance** of a research project or the **level of interdisciplinarity** may be more appropriate indicators for excellence in applied research.

Notebook writers emphasised that researchers at JR are mostly assessed as a group. Therefore, the internal understanding of excellence and success shapes the performance of the group. Therefore, **internal communication and support is seen as crucial for success**. Every member of the group has the responsibility to participate in the process of improving and reflecting the way of working together. In that sense it is important how junior researchers are treated within the group, how knowledge is passed on and how the group deals with mistakes and uncertainties in the research process.

So far, at JOANNEUM RESEARCH the following indicators are established to assess scientific excellence:

Indicators for scientificity:

- Amount of publications
- Amount of hours spend for teaching
- Amount of lectors and presentations
- Amount of events and presentations for small and medium-sized enterprises
- Amount of expert reports and reviews
- Amount of committees participated
- Public presence: amount of appearances
- Amount of prizes and awards

Indicators for invention disclosures:

- Amount of inventions disclosures
- Amount of patents
- Amount of licences
- Licence turnover in EUR

Indicators for human resources:

- Number of key researchers
- Number of researchers with an h-index over 5
- Amount of training days
- Amount of scientific theses
- Number of post-graduate studies
- Stays abroad for further training, scientific collaborations
- Visiting academics and visiting students
- Supervision of local and foreign interns

These indicators are measured for all institutes in the same way, although not all indicators are relevant for all disciplines. For example, inventions disclosures are mostly relevant for technical institutes but not for others. Publications, committees and reviews are rather relevant for fields which are closer to scientific research but not that important for technical research.

What was also mentioned in the notebooks is that not every person in a research group has the same chance to achieve good excellence indicators. Higher ranked researchers and those in leadership positions are more likely to participate in publications, lectures and presentations than lower ranked researchers. That fact makes mentoring programs and supervision of junior researchers again crucial for a fair and inclusive research process.

For these issues, some ideas to reform the assessment system at JOANNEUM RESEARCH to make it more suitable for the research practices and environment in applied research have been discussed by the notebook writers.

- Because JOANNEUM RESEARCH covers a **variety of research fields**, it is not promising to compare them by the quantity of indicators in the same way. It would be better to consider

the differences between institutes and research fields by assessing the performance. One idea that would foster that could be to **measure the quality of contributions** rather than the quantity. This could mean measure the success rate of funding awards, measuring the quality of publications and the relevance of lectures and to establish an indicator for the social relevance or the grade of interdisciplinary of research projects.

- Because research is structured in projects and researchers work in groups, it is promising to focus on the **internal communication** and intensively work on improving it. That could mean establishing **exchange formats for scientists** which enable people within one research group or across research groups to discuss problems, approaches, to reflect on mistakes and work actively together to improve working processes. What is also important in this context is to support supervision of younger researchers through more experienced researcher. At JOANNEUM RESEARCH a mentoring system and buddy systems are already established. That participatory system how daily work, teamwork and working processes are improved could be supported by some incentives.

2.4.2 Open science

Notebooks made clear that regarding open science practices major differences between institutes and research fields exist. The institutes deal with different areas of open science, have different circumstances and challenges depending on their field of study. Therefore, open science is differentiated here in the most relevant areas. However, it needs to be noted that notebook writers see an increasing relevance of open science aspects since it is increasingly required by RFOs on national and on EU level.

Generally, notebook writers as representatives of scientific staff at JOANNEUM RESEARCH would benefit from companywide guidelines regarding open science issues, opportunities to get legal support and an exchange format to discuss the topic freely.

2.4.2.1 Open access research

Open access research concerns all 7 institutes in different ways. However, as already explained in the previous chapter, publication of research results is not equally important for all research fields. Therefore, obviously open access research is more relevant to those who are more eager to publish their results. Additionally, notebook writers argued that not all research projects at JOANNEUM RESEARCH are suitable for a publication. For example, projects funded by the European Union often require publication, but outcomes of contract research projects cannot be published because of confidentiality obligations. researchers have to estimate which projects and aspect of studies can be published and where it is worth to put additional resources in the publication of results.

On the one hand, publishing articles in open access journals is seen critical because of a lack of quality assurance in some journals. On the other hand, JOANNEUM RESEARCH has collaborations with selected open access journals that are trustworthy and, based on experiences, fulfil quality criteria, like a professional and transparent review process. Therefore, one suggestion that notebook writers agreed on is to **foster these existing collaborations** and **communicate** the existing opportunities **more intensively** to researchers.

2.4.2.2 Open data

Regarding the publication of research data, technical fields have more experience with that than social or health sciences. On the one hand, in the technical field researchers are aware of the benefits

of open data for scientific discourse and motivated to publish their data, unless corporate secrets or non-disclosure agreements hinder them. On the other hand, social and health sciences deal a lot with personal data, which have to be anonymized before publishing and therefore data disclosure is more complicated in this field. Although researchers in these disciplines see a benefit in disclose research data for the scientific communities, on the one hand they might not be able to due to a lack of resources for data preparation and on the other hand through anonymization valuable information in the data is often lost. Additionally, regardless of the discipline, data disclosure goes along with maintenance, and this requires time **resources, which often are not covered by the project budget** either.

In sum, researchers see the benefit of open data, but it requires resources which are often not available. In addition to that, researchers are often uncertain if data disclosure would make sense, considering the challenges and the additional effort needed. However, in the notebooks it has also been reflected that this uncertainty might not only be a challenge but also a chance for researchers to actively shape future processes of data disclosure. Researchers would like support in disclosing and utilising public data, but there is often uncertainty about what constitutes a trustworthy platform.

At JOANNEUM RESEARCH a template for data management plans has been developed and notebook writers see that as an important step towards efficient data management, which would enable data disclosure in further consequence. Therefore, institute internal exchange about storage and usage of data and data management plans would be beneficial to deal with discipline-specific challenges.

2.4.2.3 Open-source software

Notebook writers reflected that the usage of open-source software is beneficial for scientific practises in general. Besides the practical benefit of it, it enables discourse and communication within the scientific community and opens possibilities for cooperation with different entities.

In technical fields, providing open-source software is connoted with similar challenges than providing open data, it requires additional effort for maintenance.

2.4.2.4 Scientific communication

In course of the topic open science, notebook writers also reflected scientific communication in general. Here notebook writers reflected that it must be differentiated which focus group should be addressed by scientific communication. Depending on that, different media formats are favourable. For example, elder public society needs to be addressed through newspaper, radio or television and younger public society needs to be addressed rather through social media and the scientific community itself obviously needs to be addressed on different ways. In scientific communication with the public, researchers are often concerned that information is abridged or used politically.

Further, notebook writers do not agree whether scientific communication should be a criterion for scientific excellence, which means that it is also not equally relevant for all disciplines.

2.4.3 Recruitment

The main message in the notebooks regarding that topic is that generalised assessment criteria in the recruitment process are not desirable. Rather, the assessment criteria should be specifically adjusted to the specific job advertisement.

For every position it should be defined, which social and professional competences are required. Therefore, notebook writers reflected that scientific excellence should only be a criterion for leadership positions and senior researchers, but at the same time they wish that social and soft skills would be given greater consideration in filling these positions. In general, working at JOANNEUM RESEARCH with mostly interdisciplinary approaches, the ability to be flexible and adaptive is considered favourable from all notebook writers. Therefore, for junior researchers or technicians, scientific excellence should not play a big role, but rather how open-minded applicants are and how motivated to tackle new challenges.

Taking diversity into account in the recruitment process is generally considered positively from the notebook writers. They made the experience that different approaches are fruitful for the research process and for working together in a team. Nevertheless, limits are also mentioned. While sectoral and disciplinary mobility is considered positively, because it is favourable for applied research, geographic mobility is seen critical in some contexts. As language and cultural differences are seen as an obstacle to cooperation within a research group. Further, notebook writers reflected that women at JOANNEUM RESEARCH are still underrepresented in leadership positions.

From these reflections, the following suggestions regarding the recruitment process have been made:

- Notebook writers reflected on their own experience with mistakes and all of them concluded that mistakes and failures lead to learnings. Failures cannot be avoided completely, and they always open the possibility to learn something out of it. Based on these experiences, notebook writers desire a learning culture within the company and hope that researchers become more motivated to exchange about failures and how to deal with it. Part of this discussion is also how researchers deal with negative outcomes, as failures can be educational on personal level, negative outcomes could lead to important insights for the scientific community, however mostly they are withheld. One idea that addresses these considerations in recruitment is a narrative CV. This would give applicants the opportunity to express their career in a different way and show things like mistakes or failures that would otherwise get so space.
- To encourage women to take on a management position, the already existing mentoring system at JOANNEUM RESEARCH should be fostered. In addition to that, women should be supported to assume project lead positions.
- Good experiences have been made with two-step recruitment processes. The first step would be a classical interview with the leadership and a second step a meeting with the possible future colleagues, which enables the research team to participate in the recruitment process and makes it to estimate if the applicant fits in the group.

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